

ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE: FIGHT AGAINST THE GLOBAL THREAT OF THE XXI CENTURY

Ganiyeva Shakhlo Fayzilloyevna

Lecturer at Abu Ali Ibn Sina College of Public Health

shaxloganieva70@gmail.com

Kazimova Janona Azizovna

Student of the Faculty of Pediatric Dentistry at the Tashkent State Dental Institute

kazimovajanona@gmail.com

Numonova Amina Aslamovna

Student of the Faculty of Medicine at the Samarkand State Medical Institute

meenanumonova@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The authors of the article designate as their main goal the analysis and rational approach to such a concept as antibiotic resistance (antibiotic resistance). The article contains information about the emergence of the first antibiotics, their irrational use, the emergence of superbugs resistant to many of the presented types of antimicrobial agents, statistical data around the world and methods of combating this dangerous phenomenon.

Keywords: Antibiotic resistance, resistance, penicillin, infectious diseases, efficacy, unlimited use, pan-resistance

INTRODUCTION

The picture of today shows a threatening increase in the level of antibiotic resistance around the globe. Every day, new mechanisms of the emergence and spread of resistance appear, threatening people with infectious diseases even with the simplest manipulations. The Lancet journal in one of its articles determined that the damage inflicted on the peoples of Europe from immune infections doubled in 2015 compared to 2007. A large number of infections: tuberculosis, pneumonia, gonorrhoea, blood poisoning, gastrointestinal diseases, are already difficult, and sometimes impossible to treat, due to the ineffectiveness of antimicrobial drugs. The problem is the over-the-counter sale and uncontrolled use of antibiotics by humans and on animals. Scientists predict a new era in human life, in the activity of medicine - a post-antibiotic era in which any infection will again be fatal.

METHODS

Antibiotic resistance of microbes is a phenomenon in which a microbe strain is immune to the action of one or more types of antibiotics. In fact, this is the evolution of a microorganism, in order to achieve high stability and preserve its vital activity. It is important to note that resistance is formed only in bacteria, and not in humans or animals.

With the discovery of penicillin and later other types of antibiotics by Alexander Fleming on September 30, 1928, medicine radically changed, these discoveries became a real breakthrough in the fight against previously intractable diseases. Doctors with their help have become almost omnipotent, coping with any infectious diseases with a probability of about 100%. However, there is a high possibility that in the near future most of the antibiotics used will lose their effectiveness. And the main reason is the resistance of bacteria.

Already, WHO and various medical centers predict by the beginning of the next decade (10-20 years) full resistance of microorganisms to antibiotics. This situation is a consequence of the unlimited use of antibiotics not only in medicine, but also in veterinary medicine. Knowing about the weak resistance of animals and wanting to save their livestock, farmers, along with feed, give them a huge amount of antibiotics. As a result, 90% of microbes really die, and the remaining 10% begin to develop specific resistance.

According to WHO Director Gro Harlem Brundtland: "Antibiotics were one of the main discoveries of the twentieth century, if we lose them, we will find ourselves in a new time - devoid of surgery and many other procedures associated with the risk of infection. We have to develop a new concept of antibiotic therapy - to learn to take into account not only the sensitivity of the pathogen, but also the likelihood of developing resistance in its future strains." Alexander Fleming himself in 1945, at a lecture on the occasion of awarding him the Nobel Prize, said that it was possible for bacteria to get used to penicillin.

According to statistics, more than 700 thousand people die every year from infections of resistant microorganisms all over the planet. For many patients, the time of hospitalization is lengthened. Together with multi-resistant groups of microorganisms, so-called pan-resistant species are found, those that are resistant to all drugs used. Until now, the danger from resistance has been contained by the discovery of all new types of antibacterial agents. But that was the twentieth century, the time of the "Antibiotic Boom". Then researchers annually discovered more than 10 new varieties, while now, since the beginning of the new century, only 2 new classes have been discovered.

Antibiotic resistance, in a sense, can be called a race for survival, in which each side tries to preserve the integrity of its body. Human health suffers at the same time. There is a simple formula: a bacterium + a random intake of antibiotics = a superbug. However, due to limited knowledge in this area, more and more people are consuming antibiotics uncontrollably. A striking example is antibiotic-resistant tuberculosis in Kazakhstan or the Kazakh catastrophe associated with the unlimited use of antibiotics.

Of course, do not forget that resistance is a normal phenomenon, moreover, it is very ancient. Antibiotic resistance appeared even before Fleming's discovery of penicillin. Before our appearance on Earth, bacteria had been producing substances for billions of years to fight their own kind-antibiotics. Accordingly, other bacteria began to acquire mechanisms of protection against these substances. This mechanism consists in the rearrangement of a gene, which is then passed on from generation to generation. Such genes are found even in the microflora of a Tyrolean man found in the Alps with an age of five thousand years, as well as in the permafrost of the Arctic with an age of thirty thousand years. These genes are now found anywhere in the world and appear even in non-pathogenic bacteria of the human microflora. The danger lies in the fact that even such bacteria can transmit the resistance gene to pathogenic microorganisms. In 1952, it was shown that bacteria resistant to penicillin existed before the discovery of penicillin.

At one time, epidemics of smallpox, plague and cholera easily claimed the lives of residents of entire cities. The children suffered from measles and scarlet fever, and had diphtheria. At that time, the mortality rate of more than 50% of patients was characteristic, and survival depended more on luck. Even in such conditions, measures such as vaccination and the introduction of serums were met with misunderstanding and huge resistance. Over time, however, humanity saw the benefits of such manipulations and this greatly raised the authority of the medical worker and medicine itself. With the invention of antibiotics, the proportion of mortality has become negligible. Even one of the main threats of the 20th and 21st centuries - HIV infection, doctors have taken control with the help of antiretroviral therapy. However, at the same time, the danger increased, which we did not suspect. Antibiotic resistance has introduced new rules in the methods of fighting infections.

Imagine a child of 3 years old. He lives in a poor family in Nepal or Africa and if he gets a bacterial infection, the probability of his recovery is no more than 50%. The reason for infecting a child with a resistant infection to antibiotics that have never been prescribed to him remains clear: he lives in conditions of total unsanitary conditions, comes into contact with waste products, and therefore is exposed to daily exposure to bacteria (both unstable and vice versa). But quite recently, people believed that immunity is formed with the careless use of antibacterial drugs. But now it is clear that

environmental factors play a huge role. It is obvious that reducing the number of drugs is no longer enough here, we need to think about water supply, food hygiene and sanitation in a number of regions.

Now we know that bacteria can develop resistance to the action of drugs, both by accident and by direct exchange of genetic information. In other words, a bacterium that does not have a resistance gene can instantly receive it from a neighboring bacterium that has the corresponding gene. Then they will both be able to fight the effects of the antibiotic.

Often, the emergence of resistant microorganisms occurs in hospitals, where microorganisms of the same species and different strains can easily exchange genetic information. Also, antibiotics enter the human body with plants that are now fertilized with antibiotics. People become infected with resistant bacteria that have arisen in farmlands through animal products (undercooked meat, raw foods), through contact with infected animals, as well as through vector animals (rodents, insects). Sometimes the drug is ineffective only because it is used in veterinary medicine. An interesting example of "colistin", which is effective against *E. coli*, but has not been used because of its severe side effects. In animal husbandry, it has shown excellent results as a growth stimulator for livestock. A couple of years ago, an *E. coli* resistant to colistin was discovered in a Chinese hospital. It turned out that the wand appeared in the hospital from a nearby farm, and the carrier was a fly. After that, a law was issued in China banning the addition of the drug to animal feed. Now colistin belongs to the list of reserve antibiotics used when nothing else helps.

The development of resistance and the increase in the number of incurable infections are directly proportional. According to the UN report of April 2019: in 2018, 50,000 citizens died from resistant infections in Europe and the USA, more than 700 thousand people die every year, and by 2050 this figure threatens to reach 10 million people around the globe. The number of deaths from infections of resistant microorganisms in Europe in 2016 reached 37 thousand people, while the financial damage amounted to about 7 billion euros, in animal husbandry, 20 billion dollars are lost annually because of this. In February 2017, WHO publishes the first list of antimicrobial-resistant pathogens - a total of 12 bacteria that most threaten human life and health. At the same time, all microorganisms from the WHO list are divided into 3 main groups: medium priority, high priority and extreme priority. What actions will doctors take if any operation or an open fracture threatens death, pneumonia will take the lives of 30% of patients, and treatment that reduces immunity (for example, cancer chemotherapy) becomes impossible?

ADB is implemented by the following mechanisms: efflux, or rapid removal of ABP by a microbial cell (especially effective against tetracycline antibiotics), the

ability to inactivate ABP with special cell enzymes. As a result, the antibiotic will be unable to bind to the target. An example of such enzymes is B-lactamases, which catalyze the cleavage of B-lactam rings. Metabolic bypass surgery is an alternative way to preserve the integrity of bacteria. Also, modified targets, by changing their chemical structure, become resistant to ABP.

ADB can be determined by traditional or phenotypic methods and molecular genetic methods. The phenotypic methods include: the disco-diffuse method, the method of serial dilutions (in broth and agar) and the E-test (combined). However, phenotypic methods are always difficult and dangerous. Molecular genetic methods involve manipulations with live bacteria and are characterized by high sensitivity, standardization of research and high speed of obtaining results. Rapid diagnosis of infection is important because in septic shock, every hour of delayed therapy reduces the possibility of recovery by 7.6%. Advanced companies offer to identify resistance genes by PCR. Now for this purpose there are basic sets of reagents for detecting resistance to beta-lactam and glycopeptide AB: "BakResista GLA Van/Mec" and "BakResista GLA". The material for research can be: urine, sputum, scrapings from mucous membranes, feces, exudates and bacterial cultures. Moreover, several objects are simultaneously detected in one test tube (multiplex analysis). To carry out the analysis, devices "Dtlight", "DTprime" or "DT-96" are needed.

Recently in countries such as Egypt, India, Russia, China, etc. (12 countries) a public opinion poll was conducted. The results of the survey of about 10 thousand people, published on the WHO website, really shocked the general public. The purpose of the survey was to identify people's knowledge in the field of antibiotic therapy and resistance to it. In general, only 2/3 of the respondents had an idea about drug resistance, of which 44% believe that resistance develops only in those patients who take antimicrobial drugs regularly, 76% are sure that immunity is nothing more than the "habituation" of the body of one patient to one antibiotic, 66% do think that if follow all the doctor's instructions, then the patient is not in danger of resistant germs. Of the 1,000 Russians surveyed online, 56% have taken antibiotics over the past 6 months (as prescribed by doctors), however, 67% of them were ill with SARS or flu, and as we know, antimicrobial agents are simply useless for such diseases. In addition, 25% are sure that taking these drugs should be stopped immediately after improving their health, so as not to "spoil their immunity". It is this reason that is one of the main reasons for the development of resistance.

Another little-known, but very interesting fact is the path of the spread of resistant microorganisms on our planet. So it turns out that the main carriers are tourists. Some students from Sweden, who have been studying for an exchange in Africa and India for a long time, did not get sick during their trips and did not take antibiotics, but

returned home with a strongly resistant intestinal microbiome. Most likely, the reason is the ingestion of resistant antibiotics with food or water into their body. In general, it is very interesting to observe the development of the hypothesis of the influence of the intestinal microbiota on human life and health, today this topic is especially relevant. Even when Harvard scientists deciphered the genome of gut microbes, they discovered thousands of new species of bacteria that are still unknown to mankind. The human microbiome changes with age and depends on many lifestyle factors. For example, it depends on how a person was born (by caesarean section or by natural childbirth), what kind of food he consumed in infancy (breast milk or mixtures), and most importantly, whether he was prescribed antibiotics in early childhood. Thus, it is the change in the intestinal microbiota in infancy that causes the tendency of preschool children to overweight. In the future, this threatens the development of obesity. 2 groups of children born naturally were subjected to the study. The relationship between the intestinal microbiota at 3 months and body weight at the age of 5-6 years was analyzed. Researchers have proved that there is a direct relationship between changes in the microbiota under the influence of antibiotics and body weight. So, bifidobacteria affect body weight positively, and streptococcus negatively. If their number in the microflora is detected correctly and in time, it is possible to predict the impending problems with a high probability. Consequently, any antibiotics prescribed in infancy negatively affect its future development, leading to hypertension, overweight, obesity and other diseases. So, in order to maintain health in the future, you need to prescribe medications wisely in the present.

Insensitivity to antibiotics greatly complicates the treatment of ENT diseases. The oropharynx and nasopharynx are always inhabited by countless microbes, the most dangerous of which are found in diseases such as otitis media, rhinosinusitis or tonsillopharyngitis: *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Moraxella catarrhalis*, *Haemophilus influenzae* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. The probability of self-destruction outside of antibiotic therapy is from 30 to 80%. Many of these bacteria not only cause respiratory infections, but also produce β -lactamases (for example, *Moraxella catarrhalis*), which protect pyogenic streptococcus and pneumococcus in polymicrobial infections. They inactivate antibiotics or form bacterial biofilms that also reduce their activity. Through these biofilms, resistance genes can be transmitted between different bacteria. At one of his speeches, Tedros Adan Ghebreyesus, WHO Director General, said that resistance is one of the global risks of the present time. She threatens to destroy all the medical advances she has made.

ADB- antibiotic resistance occurs in each country in its own way and depends on the method of antibiotic therapy tactics, the number of vaccinated citizens, climatic conditions. However, it is not possible to determine the sensitivity of pathogens to

antibiotics in all microbiological laboratories. This process requires certain methodological features, therefore, studies are conducted with a centralized determination of the sensitivity of isolated pathogens by the method of microintelligence.

Since 1999, the Research Institute of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy and MAKMAKH (Interregional Association for Clinical Microbiology and Antimicrobial Chemotherapy) have been conducting epidemiological studies of microbial resistance. 30 different centers in Russia take part in the research. All types of the above-mentioned bacteria are re-identified and their sensitivity is determined by the method of micro-dilution and analysis in the Smolensk Laboratory of NIIAH. Within the framework of these studies, MAKMAKH and NIIAKH created the "ADB map of Russia" - AMRmap (map.antibiotic.ru). The map allows you to reduce the time between the conducted research and the provision of results. During the entire research period (from 2013 to 2018), more than 600 strains of pyogenic streptococcus were tested, collected from patients in 14 cities of the Russian Federation. All of them were unstable to penicillin, linezolid and vancomycin. 15% of the strains were resistant to tetracycline drugs and macrolides (in children-13%), 11% - to erythromycin, 99.5% were sensitive to lincosamides. A gradual increase in the resistance of pyogenic streptococcus to drugs can be detected by comparing previous and new data: according to the PeGAS project, in 1999-2009, resistance to erythromycin was 3%, and according to 2008-2012 studies, CERBERUS determined resistance to macrolides at 8.6%. The same PEGASUS studies of 1999-2009 showed data on the resistance of pneumococci. During this period, 2,419 strains of S. were collected in the Central and Northwestern cities of Russia. Pneumoniae and collected data on resistance to penicillin- 11%, amoxicillin-0.4%, ceftriaxone-1%, macrolides-8.2%, clindamycin-2.9%, tetracycline-25%, cotrimoxazole-30% and full sensitivity to fluoroquinolones. However, according to the map of the ADB of the Russian Federation for 2013-2018, it can be seen that resistance increased by tens of percent: to penicillin- 30%, ceftriaxone-16.6%, macrolides-25%, clindamycin-15%, tetracycline-25%, cotrimoxazole-67.7%.

Data on antibiotic resistance can be obtained through the global interactive map Resistance Open (development of the HealthMap system), which provides information at a distance of 25 miles about global outbreaks of diseases, time and their pathogens, antimicrobial resistance. All data is publicly available for use. Europe has its own network, which also provides information on the dynamics of diseases and insensitivity to drugs - EARS-Net (European Network for the Supervision of Antimicrobial Resistance).

The countries of Europe and the USA realized the danger before us and are already fighting it. Measures that reduce the spread of resistance include a ban on the addition

of drugs used for humans to feed, as well as a ban on the use of growth-stimulating antibiotics on animals and birds (approximately 75% of antibiotics produced in the world are used in animal husbandry). Many countries promote the fight against uncontrolled prescribing of drugs for fungal and viral diseases, independent management of antibiotic therapy by patients and prohibit the sale of antibiotics without a prescription. Doctors mainly prescribe drugs of a narrow spectrum of action, which are focused on a specific type of microbes. If possible, before therapy, an examination is carried out for sensitivity to this type of drug.

But what can each person do? First of all, to help, to help yourself and humanity by taking all medications only as prescribed by a professional, conducting antibiotic therapy completely (Russian studies have shown that every fourth mother does not finish the course of antibiotics prescribed to her child). Also, you should not take residual medications, a couple of pills that have lain after treatment, or share them with anyone. It is important to try to prevent the infection itself: observe basic hygiene rules, wash your hands, practice safe sex, avoid contact with infected people and get vaccinated in a timely manner.

Politicians and governing bodies can also help in this matter. They should: a national action plan against antibiotic resistance, improve the quality of surveillance of resistant pathogens, strengthen and encourage infection prevention and control programs, regulate the proper use and handling of quality drugs, provide complete information on resistance statistics, and invest heavily in scientific research.

The best treatment is prevention. It is from this point of view that it is worth paying attention to the prevention of the development of infection, namely, to develop and apply vaccines. A huge plus of vaccines is that resistance to them is not developed, because they do not fight a specific strain of the microorganism, but create a specific immunity against them in advance. Especially the development of vaccines is necessary to combat infections such as Staphylococcus, which already have resistance to microbes. Of course, there is a problem of the evolution of microorganisms, as we see with the example of influenza. Unfortunately, a vaccine will have to be developed against them every year. Nevertheless, this method is currently considered the most effective.

In recent years, there has been an active development of new antibiotics that will affect the bacterium in such a way that its basic intracellular structures will be damaged and it simply will not have time to adapt. They will be able to disrupt the synthesis of the microbe membrane, proteins, and nucleic acids. However, today almost all pharmaceutical companies are not interested in the production of new types of antibiotics. The reason for this is the same resistance. It is simply unprofitable for a

company to spend a huge amount of money, time and labor on developing a drug, given that insensitivity to it has been forming for a year.

In 2016, active active substances against the bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) (*Staphylococcus* that does not harm the body) were found in the nasal cavity. The substance was given the name "Lugdunin", as well as the bacteria that synthesizes it. Lugdunin has every chance to become the founder of a new class of antibiotics "Fibupeptide".

"Teixobactin" is the name of a substance synthesized by a bacterium of the species *Eleftheria terrae*. Teixobactin easily passes many types of resistance. It acts pointwise on the molecular complexes of bacteria that cannot be changed by mutations. It is for this reason that resistance to it is simply not produced, and there are no ready-made genes for this in nature. Of course, we cannot predict the eternal positive effect of this drug, there will be an antidote to any antidote. But at least we will gain a huge amount of time to develop new drugs.

You can also combine antibiotics and alkyresorcins (molecules secreted by plants and bacteria for external protection). Aclipresorcins act on the bacterium from the inside, destroying membranes, proteins and the genome of the cell. Thus, the antibiotic gets the opportunity to affect the microbe. This combination of substances is called "superpuli" and increases the effectiveness of treatment by 1000 times, slowing resistance by 30 times.

One of the scientists from the University of Cleveland, Menachem Shoam, infected a group of mice with antibiotic-resistant *staphylococcus* (the MRSA bacterium, against which there is currently no treatment). After the manifestation of sepsis, he injected mice with molecules that prevent bacteria from producing toxins. As a result, the mouse population survived, and those that did not receive treatment died.

An interesting method of treatment has been developed by scientists from Boston University. They applied the antiseptic properties of silver by adding it to an antibiotic. Such a combination, according to their calculations, should allow killing 1000 times more bacteria.

The enemy of my enemy is my friend? This is the question scientists asked themselves when they began developing bacteriophages and viruses to fight bacteria. The advantage of their use lies in their mutation, they are also able to adapt to the resistance of bacteria. So far, this method has been poorly studied and requires further development. However, there are already examples of the effectiveness of this method. In 2018, at the University of Pittsburgh, a scientist named Graham Hatful saved a 15-year-old girl from cystic fibrosis. Initially, her lungs were transplanted, but especially resistant bacteria got into her body with them. Experimental treatment saved her from

death. The doctor injected her with a virus capable of killing this bacterium. After recovery, the girl underwent additional tests, it turned out that the bacteria showed no signs of forming resistance to viruses.

One of the most desirable methods of fighting is to retrain the bacterium itself, preventing the development of resistance. This method consists in editing the genome and is called CHAOS (Controlled Hindrance of Adaptation of Organisms — "controlled suppression of adaptations of organisms"). Only then will antibiotics become effective again and humanity will be able to control the bacteria.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In 2015, the World Health Assembly approved a Global Action Plan against Antimicrobial Resistance. The plan is aimed at the prevention and treatment of infectious diseases with safe and effective medicines. The plan includes 5 strategic objectives aimed at raising awareness, improving surveillance, reducing the number of infected, optimizing the use of drugs and sustainable investments in this area. Heads of State on Gen. The UN Assembly in September 2016 pledged to act in a coordinated manner in the fight against the causes of antibiotic resistance. In this they will all be greatly supported by WHO. There are several programs that WHO has been implementing in recent years: the Inter-Agency Coordination Group on Antimicrobial Resistance (IACG), the Global Partnership for Research and Development of Antibiotics (GARDP), the Global Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance System (GLASS), the World Week of Proper Use of Antibiotics - held in November 2015 years.

Thanks to a well-regulated action plan for propaganda in the fight against ADB, every doctor knows about the five basic rules of taking medications, which actually include antibiotics: the right patient receives the right medicine at the right time, in the right dose and the right way of use.

CONCLUSION

Programming a person's health during the first years of his life, it is important, at least, to refuse to take antimicrobial drugs during these years, and ideally to live without them at all. An alternative to such drugs may be herbal remedies that are safe for humans. It is also important to raise awareness of both ordinary patients, their parents, and doctors. Humanity needs a "golden mean" in this matter, as it always varies from complete rejection to the terrible abuse of antibiotics.

We can only hope that we will be able to evolve faster than these tiny organisms.

REFERENCES:

1. BME: Antibiotic resistance on October 16, 2011.
2. Medical Bulletin (www.medvestnik.ru). Global antibiotic resistance
3. Multidisciplinary medical center LLC "Euromed Clinic". "Antibiotic resistance: a race for survival"
4. <https://gp1.zdrav36.ru/> BUZ VO "VGPK 1" What is antibiotic resistance?
5. OBUZ "Ivanovo Regional Clinical Hospital" Antibiotic resistance. September 30, 2019
6. <http://gorkicrb.by/antibiotikorezistentnost/> Healthcare institution "Goretsky Central District Hospital". Antibiotic resistance
7. Breast cancer (Russian Medical Journal): "Antibiotic resistance of the main pathogens of ENT diseases"
8. World Health Organization. Antibiotic resistance <https://www.who.int/ru>
9. NPS MedicineWise <https://www.nps.org.au/publications/health-professional/health-news-evidence/2013/duration-of-antibiotic-therapy>
10. World Health Organization. Antimicrobial resistance. <https://www.who.int/en/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/antimicrobial-resistance>
11. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. «About Antibiotic Resistance»
12. WHO <https://www.who.int/home/cms-decommissioning>
13. Review on Antimicrobial Resistance. <https://amr-review.org/>
14. THE RESISTANCE OF MICROBES TO ANTIBIOTICS IS A GLOBAL PROBLEM OF MANKIND. FSBI "VGNKI"
15. Antibiotic resistance: how scientists around the world are already fighting the next pandemic. <https://www.admnvrsk.ru/o-gorode/novosti/glavnye-novosti/news-05032021112500-87215/>
16. ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE OF "BakResista GLA" "BakResista GLA Van/Mec" https://dna-technology.ru/sites/default/files/BakRezista_114-2.pdf
17. General Principles of Antimicrobial Therapy. [https://www.mayoclinicproceedings.org/article/S0025-6196\(11\)60140-7/pdf](https://www.mayoclinicproceedings.org/article/S0025-6196(11)60140-7/pdf)
18. Wikipedia. "Antimicrobial resistance"
19. Agrarian science of Euro-North-East 2018. Antibiotic resistance: evolutionary prerequisites, mechanisms, consequences.
20. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/antibiotikorezistentnost-v-sovremennom-mire/viewer>